

A Study of Inhibiting Action of some Monosaccharides on Corrosion of Zinc in HNO₃

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The inhibition of corrosion of zinc in 1.5 M nitric acid, by some monosaccharides (glucose, fructose, mannose, galactose) in the concentration range 5×10^{-3} – 3×10^{-1} M has been studied with respect to concentration of inhibitor and period of immersion. In general, the inhibitor efficiency increases with increase in concentration of inhibitor

NUMEROUS studies have shown that glucose can almost completely inhibit the corrosion of copper and of its zinc alloys in alkaline¹, ammoniacal², and neutral³ environments although the mechanism of inhibition is still much debated. According to some authors, the inhibition is due to a protective film formed by the corrosion products, while according to others²⁻⁴, glucose acts as a secondary inhibitor, removing oxygen from the solution, thus preventing cathodic reduction of oxygen. According to some authors, glucose at concentrations of 5×10^{-3} – 5×10^{-1} M prevents the corrosion of iron⁵ and copper in 1 M HNO₃ at 20° C.

To check the inhibitive efficiency of monosaccharides in general, and to work out a possible hypothesis regarding the mechanism of inhibition, a series of experiments were performed with 1.5 M HNO₃ in presence of various concentrations of monosaccharides.

Experimental

The monosaccharides (AnalaR) were used as such. The inhibitor solution was prepared in double-distilled water (100 ml). A 1.5 M HNO₃ was prepared from standard 5 M HNO₃.

Zinc specimens (99.999% Zn) were cut rectangular (20×20×1 mm) for weight-loss measurements, while for polarisation measurements they were cylindrical. The electrodes were of 0.8 cm in dia and 1 cm in length. All specimens were treated with a series of successive grades of emery papers and degreased with an alkaline solution (15 g Na₂CO₃+15 g Na₂PO₄/dm³), then washed several times by distilled water and dried before being immersed in the corrosive solution.

Polarisation measurements: Anodic polarisation experiments were carried out under unstirred condition with a fine Luggin capillary to avoid

ohmic polarisation. Galvanostatic conditions were maintained using a WP-704 AX potentiostat. Zinc was taken in the form of cylindrical rods with an area of 0.50 cm². A saturated calomel electrode and a platinum electrode were used as reference and auxiliary electrodes respectively. The potentials were recorded using a Orion 701A digital ionalyser. For each experiment a new specimen was used

Each series of experiments was carried out in duplicate and the results were reproducible to within ±5%.

Results and Discussion

The data obtained for the electrochemical and corrosion behaviour of zinc in 1.5 M HNO₃ in the absence and presence of glucose within the concentration range 5×10^{-3} to 3×10^{-1} M are given in Table 1. The results indicate that glucose has inhibitive effect on the corrosion of zinc in HNO₃ solution. Similar results were

TABLE 1—ELECTROCHEMICAL DATA* FOR INHIBITION OF CORROSION OF ZINC IN 1.5 M HNO₃ USING DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION OF GLUCOSE AT 20°

Concn. of glucose M	-E _{corr} mV	I _{corr} mA cm ⁻²	b _a mV/dec.	θ	P _{i,corr} %
0.3	721	2.45	180	0.28	38.4
0.25	725	2.63	170	0.26	33.9
0.20	733	2.82	178	0.20	29.1
0.15	745	2.95	174	0.18	25.9
0.05	750	3.09	186	0.14	22.4
0	780	3.98	158		

*E_{corr} = Corrosion potential, mV (open-circuit potential), I_{corr} = corrosion current, mA cm⁻² (intercept of Tafel line with E_{corr}), b_a = anodic Tafel slope mV/decade, θ = degree of surface coverage, P_i - protection efficiency

$$(\%P_i = \frac{(I_{free} - I_{inh.})}{I_{free}} \times 100)$$

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obtained for the other monosaccharides (fructose, mannose and galactose). However, their inhibition efficiencies (expressed as P_i) are relatively low and ranged from 20 to 40% (Table 2). Similar results were obtained by Maria and Mor⁷ for the inhibitive effect of some monosaccharides for the corrosion

TABLE 2—EFFICIENCY OF CORROSION INHIBITION AS DETERMINED BY POLARISATION AND WEIGHT-LOSS METHODS AT $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ AND 30°

Compd.	% Inhibition	
	Polarisation	Weight-loss
Glucose	22.4	11.4
Fructose	21.5	10.5
Mannose	19.9	10.0
Galactose	18.7	9.8

of copper in NH_3 solutions. Fig. 1 shows the anodic polarisation curves of zinc in $1.5 M HNO_3$ at different concentrations of glucose at a temperature of 30° . Similar curves were obtained for the other three monosaccharides. The anodic polarisation curves shifted to more positive values in the presence of glucose (Fig. 1). This indicates that the zinc electrode is anodically polarised.

Fig. 1. Anodic Tafel plots for Zn in $1.5 M HNO_3$ at different concentrations of glucose and at 30° : (a) blank, (b) 0.05, (c) 0.15, (d) 0.20, (e) 0.25 and (f) 0.30 M.

The inhibition of corrosion of zinc in HNO_3 solution in presence of these monosaccharides is due only to the oxidation of glucose by nitric acid⁸. In an acid environment, nitric acid will oxidise the carbonyl groups of all of the monosaccharides to the carboxyl group, transforming them to gluconic or tartaric acid, or decomposing

them into oxalic acid⁹. The data reported in the reference literature indicate that oxidation of monosaccharides is more readily brought about by nitric acid.

The mechanism of inhibition may be complicated. The monosaccharides could act as indirect inhibitors reducing the concentration of HNO_3 . They could also act as true primary inhibitors, forming complexes with zinc which would precipitate on the corroded surface affording some protection. The presence of an organic compound on the surface of specimens which had been etched at 30° was confirmed spectrophotometrically. Qualitative and quantitative analyses were also performed on the corrosion product to determine its zinc content. It was found that the quantity of zinc found in solution was indeed negligible and probably due to the presence of zinc oxides. The undissolved product, after the decomposition of organic matter, was washed, filtered and dried at room temperature, and then analysed chemically for zinc. An amount not more than 10% of the dissociated corrosion product for the various monosaccharides was found. This zinc content in the corrosion products is significant and seems to indicate the formation of an organometallic compound rather than its adsorption on the corroded surface.

Fig. 2. Variation of weight-loss of zinc with immersion time in $1.5 M HNO_3$ with and without different concentrations of glucose at 30° : (a) $1 N HNO_3$; (b) 0.05, (c) 0.10, (d) 0.15, (e) 0.20, (f) 0.25 and (g) 0.30 M.

The free dissolution of zinc in 1.5 M HNO₃ with and without additives (monosaccharides) was carried out by the weight-loss method for 90 min immersion at 30°. Fig. 2 shows the weight-loss-time curves in presence and in absence of different concentrations of glucose. Similar curves were obtained for the other monosaccharides. The extent of inhibition of corrosion for all the compounds was found to depend on the concentration of the inhibitor and time of immersion.

Conclusions: It has been shown that the saccharides have a moderate inhibitive efficiency towards zinc in nitric acid, but only at relatively high concentrations (0.3 M).

The kind of structure of the various saccharides investigated does not affect their inhibitive efficiency for zinc in nitric acid. They could act not only as indirect inhibitors, reducing the concentration of HNO₃, but could also act as primary inhibitors forming complexes with zinc which would precipitate on the zinc surface affording some protection.

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